

The relationship between earthquake preparedness, perceived earthquake risk, and anxiety among adults

Yetişkinlerde deprem hazırlığı, algılanan deprem riski ve kaygı arasındaki ilişki

Merve Kolcu¹, Aydan Yılmaz², Seda Ayyıldız³, Zeynep Düz⁴, Yüsrnur Dirikolu⁵, Feride Güzel⁶, Sümeyya Ay⁷, Fatma Aslan⁸, Haibier Rexıdai⁹, İrem Büyükakça¹⁰

¹ Associate Prof., PhD, RN, Department of Public Health Nursing, Hamidiye Faculty of Nursing, University of Health Sciences, Istanbul/Turkey, merve.kolcu@sbu.edu.tr, 0000-0002-8187-4767

² MSc, RN, Department of Public Health Nursing, Hamidiye Faculty of Nursing, University of Health Sciences, Istanbul, Turkey, aydan.yilmaz@sbu.edu.tr, 0000-0001-7494-976X

³ Dr. Hem., SBÜ Zeynep Kamil Kadın ve Çocuk Hastalıkları Eğitim ve Araştırma Hastanesi, Enfeksiyon Kontrol Komitesi, İstanbul/ Türkiye, sedaoltulu_89@hotmail.com, 0000-0003-2664-0615

⁴ Nursing Student, Hamidiye Faculty of Nursing, University of Health Sciences, Istanbul, Turkey, zeynepduz78@outlook.com, 0009-0003-9845-3824

⁵ Nursing Student, Hamidiye Faculty of Nursing, University of Health Sciences, Istanbul, Turkey, 2202001013@ogrenci.sbu.edu.tr, 0009-0005-3393-463X

⁶ Nursing Student, Hamidiye Faculty of Nursing, University of Health Sciences, Istanbul, Turkey, guzelferide6@gmail.com, 0009-0001-8535-5147

⁷ Nursing Student, Hamidiye Faculty of Nursing, University of Health Sciences, Istanbul, Turkey, sumeyyeay47@gmail.com, 0009-0005-8472-7921

⁸ Nursing Student, Hamidiye Faculty of Nursing, University of Health Sciences, Istanbul, Turkey, 2202001061@ogrenci.sbu.edu.tr, 0009-0007-3575-2228

⁹ Nursing Student, Hamidiye Faculty of Nursing, University of Health Sciences, Istanbul, Turkey, rexide.gb@gmail.com, 0009-0007-6826-7616

¹⁰ Nursing Student, Hamidiye Faculty of Nursing, University of Health Sciences, Istanbul, Turkey, irembykca@gmail.com, 0009-0007-4032-4156

ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the relationship between earthquake preparedness, perceived earthquake risk, and anxiety among adults. This descriptive study was conducted with 286 individuals who participated in an online survey between May and August 2025. Data were collected using a questionnaire, which included the Earthquake Preparedness Behavior Scale, the Earthquake Risk Perception Scale, and the Earthquake Anxiety Scale. Descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation analysis were employed for data analysis. The mean total score of the Earthquake Preparedness Behavior Scale was 9.75 ± 3.50 , the mean total score of the Earthquake Risk Perception Scale was 27.60 ± 3.38 , and the mean total score of the Earthquake Anxiety Scale was 27.60 ± 3.38 . A statistically significant positive correlation was found between the total score of the Earthquake Preparedness Behavior Scale and the total scores of both the Earthquake Risk Perception Scale and the Earthquake Anxiety Scale ($p < 0.001$). The findings of this study indicate a significant positive relationship between earthquake preparedness behavior, risk perception, and earthquake anxiety levels. This suggests that risk perception and anxiety are important factors influencing individuals' level of earthquake preparedness.

Anahtar Kelimeler:

Earthquake Preparedness, Earthquake Risk Perception, Earthquake Anxiety

Corresponding Author/Sorumlu Yazar:

Doç. Dr. Merve KOLCU, Sağlık Bilimleri Üniversitesi Hamidiye Hemşirelik Fakültesi İstanbul/Türkiye, merve.kolcu@sbu.edu.tr, 0000-0002-8187-4767

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.18054181

Received Date/Gönderme Tarihi:

09.10.2025

Accepted Date/Kabul Tarihi:

11.12.2025

Published Online/Yayımlanma Tarihi

31.12.2025

ÖZ

Bu çalışmada, yetişkin bireylerde depreme hazırlıklı olma durumu, deprem risk algısı ve anksiyete ilişkisinin belirlenmesi amaçlanmıştır. Tanımlayıcı tipte olan bu araştırma Mayıs-Ağustos 2025 tarihleri arasında çevrim içi anket katılan 286 birey ile yürütülmüştür. Verilerin toplanmasında; anket formu, Depreme Hazırlıklı Olma Davranışı Ölçeği, Deprem Risk Algısı Ölçeği ve Deprem Anksiyetesi Ölçeği kullanılmıştır. Verilerin analizinde; tanımlayıcı istatistikler ve pearson korelasyon analizi kullanılmıştır. Depreme Hazırlıklı Olma Davranışı Ölçeği toplam puan ortalaması 9.75 ± 3.50 , Bireylerin Deprem Risk Algısı Ölçeği toplam puan ortalaması 27.60 ± 3.38 , Deprem Anksiyetesi Ölçeği toplam puan ortalaması ise 27.60 ± 3.38 olarak bulunmuştur. Depreme Hazırlıklı Olma Davranışı Ölçeği toplam puanı ile Deprem Risk Algısı Ölçeği toplam puanı ve Deprem Anksiyetesi Ölçeği toplam puanı arasında istatistiksel olarak pozitif yönde anlamlı ilişki olduğu görülmüştür ($p < 0.001$). Araştırma sonuçları, depreme hazırlıklı olma davranışı, bireylerin deprem risk algısı ve deprem anksiyetesi düzeyleri ile pozitif yönde anlamlı bir ilişki göstermektedir. Bu durum, risk algısı ve anksiyetenin, bireylerin deprem hazırlık düzeylerini etkileyen önemli faktörler olduğunu ortaya koymaktadır.

Key Words:

Depreme Hazırlık, Deprem Risk Algısı, Deprem Kaygısı

INTRODUCTION

Earthquakes, as in many parts of the world, are natural disasters in Turkey that cause significant loss of life and property and are difficult to predict (Topal, Başpınar & Güntürkün, 2024; Mızrak, Özdemir & Aslan, 2021). A large proportion of disaster-related deaths and economic losses worldwide result from earthquakes; therefore, earthquakes represent not only physical destruction but also social, economic, and psychological consequences at both individual and societal levels (Wang et al., 2021). The geological structure of Turkey and its location on active fault lines make the country one of the regions with the highest earthquake risk. Indeed, large-scale earthquakes experienced in recent years have brought issues such as disaster management, community resilience, and individual preparedness to the forefront of the agenda (Topal, Başpınar & Güntürkün, 2024).

Preparedness for earthquakes is one of the fundamental determinants in reducing disaster-related losses. This encompasses not only physical preparations (e.g., preparing an emergency kit, identifying safe areas, developing an evacuation plan) but also individuals' level of knowledge, awareness, risk perception, and psychological resilience. The literature indicates that risk perception regarding disasters is a factor that directly influences individuals' preparedness behaviors. A high level of risk perception may encourage individuals to take protective and preventive measures, whereas a low level of risk perception may lead to insufficient levels of preparedness. However, excessively high-risk perception may also result in persistent anxiety, fear, and feelings of helplessness, thereby adversely affecting functionality (Trumbo et al., 2016; Gül, 2024).

One of the most observed psychological responses to disasters is anxiety. The destructive effects of earthquakes cause individuals to experience prolonged anxiety not only during the event itself but also in its aftermath. It has been reported that individuals with prior earthquake experience tend to exhibit higher levels of anxiety, which adversely affects both their daily life activities and future planning (Kahraman & Çubukcu, 2025; Uğur, Kartal & Mete, 2021). While anxiety may stimulate preparedness behaviors in some individuals, in others it can lead to dysfunctional coping strategies such as avoidance, denial, or catastrophizing. Therefore, understanding the relationship between anxiety and earthquake preparedness is crucial in planning pre- and post-disaster interventions (TUIK, 2022).

Adults occupy a key position in disaster preparedness due to their decisive roles within their families and immediate social environments. The risk perception, preparedness levels, and anxiety status of adults directly affect not only their own safety but also the safety of those under their care. Accordingly, an analysis of the relationship between adults' earthquake preparedness, risk perception, and anxiety levels is essential for the formulation of effective community-based disaster management strategies (TUIK, 2022; Zhou et al., 2017).

This study aims to examine the relationship between earthquake preparedness, earthquake risk perception, and anxiety among adults. The findings obtained are expected to contribute to the development of disaster preparedness programs, the strengthening of risk communication processes, and the planning of psychosocial support interventions before disasters. In this way, it may be possible to enhance resilience against disasters at both individual and societal levels.

METHODS

Study Design and Participants

The population of this descriptive study consists of 56.592,570 individuals aged 18-65 residing in Turkey, according to the results of the Address-Based Population Registration System (TUIK, 2022). Based on the sample size calculation formula for a known population, it was determined that at least 286 adult individuals should be included in the study.

Data were collected between May and August 2025 through an online survey using the snowball sampling method, from adults aged 18–65 who agreed to participate in the study and completed the questionnaire in full. The sample included 286 literate adults without communication impairments who were able to complete the online survey.

Measurements

Data for the study were collected using a structured questionnaire, which included the Earthquake Preparedness Behavior Scale, the Earthquake Risk Perception Scale, and the Earthquake Anxiety Scale.

Questionnaire form

The questionnaire collected information on adults' demographic characteristics (age, gender, marital status, educational level, occupation, and monthly income), knowledge of the earthquake risk in their residential area, and concerns about potential earthquake risk in their region. The form consisted of a total of 10 items.

Earthquake preparedness behavior scale

The Earthquake Preparedness Behavior Scale, developed by Wang et al. (2021) and adapted into Turkish by Topal et al. (2024), comprises 13 items across three subscales: material preparedness, behavioral preparedness, and awareness-based preparedness. None of the items require reverse scoring. In accordance with the original version of the scale, responses are collected. The same scoring method is applied to the overall scale and its subscales, with the total score representing the participant's level of preparedness. The scale demonstrated acceptable internal consistency, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.70 (Topal, Başpınar & Güntürkün, 2024; Wang, Han & Liu, 2021).

Earthquake risk perception scale

This scale is used to assess earthquake risk perception and was originally developed by Trumbo et al. (2016) to measure sensory and cognitive risk perceptions related to hurricanes (Trumbo et al., 2016). It has been indicated that the scale can be generalized to all natural disasters, and when applied to a disaster other than hurricanes, only the name of the disaster needs to be replaced. Mızrak et al. adapted the scale for earthquakes and conducted its Turkish validity and reliability study. The scale consists of eight items rated on a five-point Likert-type scale, with no reverse-scored items. It includes two subscales: sensory risk perception and cognitive risk perception. Participants are asked to select

the option that best reflects their perception of earthquake-related risk. Higher mean or total scores indicate higher levels of risk perception. The Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of the scale was reported as 0.85, demonstrating good internal consistency (Mızrak, Özdemir & Aslan, 2021).

Earthquake anxiety scale

Developed by Gül (2024), this scale uses a five-point Likert-type format. Scores on the scale range from 9 to 45, with no reverse-scored items. In the scale interpretation, scores of 9-21 indicate low anxiety, 22–33 indicate moderate anxiety, and 34- 45 indicate high anxiety (Gül, 2024).

Statistical Analysis

The data obtained from the study were analyzed using SPSS 25.0 (IBM, Armonk, NY, USA). Descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation tests were used for data analysis. Results were evaluated at a 95% confidence interval, with the significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

Ethical Consideration

The study was conducted in accordance with the Helsinki Declaration after obtaining ethical approval (dated May 29, 2025; number 12/8). The purpose and procedures of the study were explained in writing to all participants included in the research. Data were collected only after each participant provided written informed consent.

RESULTS

Among the participants, 75.9% were female, 73.1% were single, 71.7% were university graduates, 53.8% were students, and 55.6% reported that their income met their expenses. Regarding earthquake-related perceptions, 80.4% considered the province they live in as risky, 79.7% had experienced an earthquake in the past year, 64.7% did not feel prepared for an earthquake, and 81.2% reported being concerned about earthquake risk. The mean age of the participants was 26.89 ± 10.57 years (Table 1).

Table 1. Descriptive characteristics of the participants (n = 286)

Characteristics	n	%
Gender		
Female	217	75.9
Male	69	24.1
Marital Status		
Married	77	26.9
Single	209	73.1
Education		
Primary school	18	6.3
Middle school	12	4.2
High school	41	14.3
University	205	71.7
Graduate school	10	3.5

Table 1. (Devam) Descriptive characteristics of the participants (n = 286)

Characteristics	n	%
Occupation		
Self-employed	44	15.4
Student	154	53.8
Worker / employee	26	9.1
Homemaker	40	14.0
Unemployed	22	7.7
Monthly income		
Income does not meet expenses	107	37.4
Income meets expenses	159	55.6
Income exceeds expenses	20	7.0
Perception of living in a risky province		
Yes	230	80.4
No	9	3.1
Partially	47	16.5
Experienced an earthquake in the past year		
Yes	228	79.7
No	58	20.3
Perceived earthquake preparedness		
Yes	18	6.3
No	185	64.7
Partially	83	29.0
Concern about earthquake risk		
Yes	232	81.2
No	15	5.2
Partially	39	13.6
	Mean ± SD.	Min.- Max.
Age	26.89±10.57	18-63

SS.: Standard Deviation; Min.-Max.: Minimum-Maximum

The score distributions for the Earthquake Preparedness Behavior Scale, Earthquake Risk Perception Scale, and Earthquake Anxiety Scale are presented in Table 2. For the Earthquake Preparedness Behavior Scale, the mean score for the material preparedness subscale was 3.56 ± 1.91 (range: 0–7), for the behavioral preparedness subscale 3.13 ± 1.45 (range: 0–5), for the awareness-based preparedness subscale 3.04 ± 1.20 (range: 0–4), and the total score was 9.75 ± 3.50 (range: 0–16). The mean score for the sensory risk perception subscale of the Earthquake Risk Perception Scale was 14.57 ± 2.15 (range: 8–19), for the cognitive risk perception subscale 16.31 ± 1.94 (range:

8–20), and the total score was 30.88 ± 2.94 (range: 23–38). The mean total score of the Earthquake Anxiety Scale was 27.60 ± 3.38 (range: 19–37) (Table 2).

Table 2. Score distributions of the Earthquake Preparedness Behavior Scale, Earthquake Risk Perception Scale, and Earthquake Anxiety Scale

Scales	Mean±SD.	Min.-Max.
Earthquake Preparedness Behavior Scale		
Material Preparedness	3.56±1.91	0-7
Behavioral Preparedness	3.13±1.45	0-5
Awareness-Based Preparedness	3.04±1.20	0-4
Total Score	9.75±3.50	0-16
Earthquake Risk Perception Scale		
Sensory Risk Perception	14.57±2.15	8-19
Cognitive Risk Perception	16.31±1.94	8-20
Total Score	30.88±2.94	23-38
Earthquake Anxiety Scale		
Total Score	27.60±3.38	19-37

SD.: Standart Deviation; Min.-Max.: Minimum-Maximum

The relationships among the Earthquake Preparedness Behavior Scale, Earthquake Risk Perception Scale, and Earthquake Anxiety Scale were examined. A statistically significant positive correlation was observed between the total score of the Earthquake Preparedness Behavior Scale and the total scores of both the Earthquake Risk Perception Scale and the Earthquake Anxiety Scale ($p < 0.001$) (Table 3).

Table 3. Relationships among the Earthquake Preparedness Behavior Scale, Earthquake Risk Perception Scale, and Earthquake Anxiety Scale

Scales	Earthquake Preparedness Behaviour Scale	Earthquake Risk Perception Scale	Earthquake Anxiety Scale
Earthquake Preparedness Behaviour Scale	1	0.076*	0.018*

* Pearson correlation $p < 0.01$

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study provide important insights into adults' preparedness, risk perception, and anxiety levels related to earthquakes. The majority of participants were female (75.9%), single (73.1%), university graduates (71.7%), and students (53.8%). This demographic distribution represents a significant sample for evaluating earthquake preparedness and risk perception among young and educated individuals. The predominance of students highlights the need to focus on disaster awareness and preparedness behaviors in the younger population. Previous literature also indicates that, although

young adults tend to have relatively high awareness of disasters, their actual preparedness behaviors remain limited (Topal, Başpınar, & Güntürkün, 2024; Mızrak, Özdemir & Aslan, 2021; Trumbo et al., 2016).

In the study, 80.4% of participants considered their province to be at risk for earthquakes, and 79.7% had experienced an earthquake in the past year, indicating that individuals are aware of the likelihood of earthquakes in their environment. Nevertheless, 64.7% reported not feeling prepared for an earthquake, and 81.2% expressed concern about earthquake risk. These findings confirm the frequently emphasized “risk perception–preparedness gap” in the literature, where individuals are aware of earthquake hazards, but this awareness does not always translate into behavioral preparedness. Possible reasons for this gap include lack of knowledge, economic constraints, fatalistic beliefs, and psychological barriers related to disasters. In this context, nurses—particularly in the field of public health—can play a critical role (Agarwalla et al., 2020). Public health nurses can organize educational programs, counselling, and awareness initiatives to enhance individuals’ earthquake awareness, support their behavioral preparedness, and address their psychosocial needs (Yan et al., 2015).

Analysis of the Earthquake Preparedness Behavior Scale revealed that the material preparedness subscale (3.56 ± 1.91) scored higher than the behavioral (3.13 ± 1.45) and awareness (3.04 ± 1.20) subscales. This finding indicates that individuals tend to focus more on tangible and visible preparedness measures (e.g., preparing an emergency kit, storing food and water) while remaining insufficient in behavioral preparedness (e.g., developing an evacuation plan, identifying safe areas) and cognitive/awareness aspects. However, behavioral preparedness is one of the most critical components in disaster management. A lack of knowledge about appropriate actions during an earthquake or low awareness can limit the effectiveness of material preparations (Rezabeigi Davarani et al., 2023; Vrselja, Pandžić & Glavaš, 2023). Therefore, individuals should be encouraged to move beyond material-based preparedness and strengthen their preparedness at the behavioral level.

According to the Earthquake Risk Perception Scale findings, participants exhibited high sensory (14.57 ± 2.15) and cognitive (16.31 ± 1.94) risk perceptions. This high level of risk perception indicates that individuals are aware of the destructive potential of earthquakes. The literature suggests that risk perception is one of the strongest predictors of preparedness behaviors (Aksa et al., 2020; Ma et al., 2023). However, in this study, despite high-risk perception, preparedness levels remained moderate, suggesting a perception–behavior inconsistency among individuals. One possible explanation is that high risk perception may induce excessive anxiety and feelings of helplessness, preventing translation into actionable behaviors. Indeed, some studies have reported that excessively high-risk perception can lead to catastrophizing and avoidance responses rather than promoting preparedness behaviors (Thapa et al., 2018).

Analysis of the Earthquake Anxiety Scale revealed a high mean score (27.60 ± 3.38), indicating that anxiety related to earthquakes is a common psychological response in the population. Earthquake-related anxiety can have both facilitating and inhibiting effects on individuals’ preparedness behaviors (Thapa et al., 2018; Uğur et al., 2021).

The study found a significant positive correlation between the Earthquake Anxiety Scale and the Earthquake Preparedness Behavior Scale, suggesting that anxiety may motivate preparedness behaviors up to a certain level. Similarly, Thapa et al. (2018) and Kahraman et al. (2025) emphasized

that disaster-related anxiety can enhance preparedness behaviors, whereas excessive anxiety may impair functionality. This finding indicates that earthquake-related anxiety should not be considered entirely negative, although excessive levels may pose a risk to mental health (Zhou et al., 2017; Thapa et al., 2018).

One of the key contributions of this study is the demonstration of a positive relationship among earthquake preparedness, risk perception, and anxiety. The findings indicate that psychological factors play a critical role in disaster preparedness, and that individuals should be supported not only in physical preparedness but also in cognitive and emotional domains. The predominance of young and student populations highlights the need to strengthen disaster education, psychosocial resilience programs, and risk communication strategies for this group. Nurses, particularly in the field of public health, can play a vital role by organizing educational programs to enhance earthquake awareness, supporting behavioral preparedness, and implementing interventions to promote psychosocial resilience.

This study has several limitations. First, the data were collected via an online survey, which excluded individuals without internet access, those with limited technological skills, or those unwilling to participate in online research. Additionally, the data were obtained from a specific sample during a defined period, which limits the generalizability of the findings to the broader adult population.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study provides important contributions to the disaster management literature by revealing the interrelationships among earthquake preparedness, risk perception, and anxiety. The findings indicate that disaster preparedness programs should not be limited to the provision of material resources, but should also focus on enhancing individuals' behavioral skills and psychological resilience. In this context, it is essential to develop holistic and multidimensional approaches in community-based disaster management strategies that take into account both risk perception and anxiety. Nurses play a critical role in pre- and post-disaster processes; public health nurses can directly contribute to disaster preparedness and response at both individual and community levels by increasing earthquake awareness, supporting behavioral preparedness, and addressing psychosocial needs.

The findings of this study offer significant implications for nursing practice and public health. Nurses play a critical role in enhancing individuals' disaster preparedness, strengthening risk perception, and supporting coping with anxiety. The results highlight the need for nurses to take an active role, particularly given that a substantial proportion of individuals do not feel prepared for earthquakes and exhibit only moderate preparedness behaviors. Public health nurses can implement educational, counseling, and informational interventions to increase awareness of earthquake risk. In this context, home visits, community awareness campaigns, and school-based education programs can contribute to the development of a culture of earthquake preparedness.

REFERENCES

Agarwalla, R., Pathak, R., Siddiqui, A., Panda, M., Gupta, E., ve Islam, F. (2020). A community-based intervention study to assess the effectiveness of awareness imparted on earthquake preparedness among the residents of South Delhi, India. *Indian Journal of Community Medicine*, 45(3), 375-378. DOI: 10.4103/ijcm.IJCM_404_19.

- Gül, Y. E. (2024). Development of the Earthquake Anxiety Scale: Validity and Reliability Study. *Uluslararası Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey Eğitim Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 6(1), 25-31. DOI: 10.47770/ukmead.1389678.
- Kahraman, A., ve Çubukçu, E. (2025). Earthquake anxiety and sleep quality among adolescent survivors 9–12 months after the great earthquakes in Türkiye: a cross-sectional study. *Scientific Reports*, 15 (1), 25719. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-025-10258-w.
- Ma, Z., Zhou, W., Deng, X., ve Xu, D. (2023). Community disaster resilience and risk perception in earthquake-stricken areas of China. *Disaster Medicine and Public Health Preparedness*, 17, e74. DOI: 10.1017/dmp.2021.342.
- Mızrak, S., Özdemir, A. ve Aslan, R. (2021). Kasırga risk algısı ölçeğinin deprem risk algısına uyarlanması ve kadınların deprem risk algısını etkileyen faktörlerin belirlenmesi. *Doğal Afetler*, 109(3), 2241- 2259. DOI: 10.1007/s11069-021-04918-z.
- Rezabeigi Davarani, E., Nekoei-Moghadam, M., Khanjani, N., Iranpour, A., Chashmyazdan, M., ve Farahmandnia, H. (2023). Factors related to earthquake preparedness of households based on social-cognitive theory constructs: A systematic review. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 11, 987418. DOI: 10.3389/fpubh.2023.987418.
- Topal, M. H., Başpınar, A., ve Güntürkün, M. (2024). Social-cognitive factors of individual earthquake preparedness behavior: A scale adaptation and correlational survey research. *TRC Journal of Humanitarian Action*, 4(1). DOI: 10.55280/trcjha.2024.3.1.0099
- Trumbo, CW, Peek, L., Meyer, MA, Marlatt, HL, Grunfest, E., McNoldy, BD ve Schubert, WH (2016). Kasırga risk algısı için bilişsel-duygusal bir ölçek. *Risk Analizi*, 36(12), 2233-2246. DOI: 10.1111/risa.12575.
- Türkiye İstatistik Kurumu (TÜİK). (2022). Adrese Dayalı Nüfus Kayıt Sistemi Sonuçları, 2022. Türkiye İstatistik Kurumu. <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=49685>, Erişim Tarihi: 8 Haziran 2025.
- Thapa, P., Acharya, L., Bhatta, B. D., Paneru, S. B., Khattri, J. B., Chakraborty, P. K., ve Sharma, R. (2018). Anxiety, depression and post-traumatic stress disorder after earthquake. *J Nepal Health Res Counc*, 16(1), 53-57. DOI: 10.3126/jnhrc.v16i1.19366.
- Uğur, M., Kartal, F., Mete, B., Tamam, L., ve Demirkol, M. E. (2021). Deprem sonrası akut stres bozukluğu olanlarda travma esnasındaki çözülmenin, anksiyete düzeyi, algılanan stres, anksiyete duyarlılığı ve deprem stresiyile baş etme ile ilişkisi. *Türk Psikiyatri Dergisi*, 32(4), 253- 260. DOI: 10.5080/u25892.
- Utaya, S., Aksa, F. I., Bachri, S., ve Handoyo, B. (2020). The role of knowledge and fatalism in college students related to the earthquake-risk perception. *Jambá: Journal of Disaster Risk Studies*, 12(1), 1-6. DOI: 10.4102/jamba.v12i1.954.
- Vrselja, I., Pandžić, M., ve Glavaš, D. (2023). Predicting earthquake preparedness intention among Croatian residents: Application of the theory of planned behaviour. *International Journal of Psychology*, 58(2), 124-133. DOI: 10.1002/ijop.12882.
- Yan, Y. E., Turale, S., Stone, T., ve Petrini, M. (2015). Disaster nursing skills, knowledge and attitudes required in earthquake relief: Implications for nursing education. *International Nursing Review*, 62(3), 351-359. DOI: 10.1111/inr.12175.
- Zhou, X., Wu, X., Chen, Q., ve Zhen, R. (2017). Why did adolescents have sleep problems after earthquakes? Understanding the role of traumatic exposure, fear, and PTSD. *Scandinavian Journal of Psychology*, 58(3), 221-227. DOI: 10.1111/sjop.12366.
- Wang, Z., Han, Z., Liu, L., ve Yu, S. (2021). Place attachment and household disaster preparedness: Examining the mediation role of self-efficacy. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(11), 5565. DOI: 10.3390/ijerph18115565.